

The Intensity of Local Competition on a Global Level

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The variable "Intensity of Local Competition" refers to the degree of rivalry among businesses operating within a specific geographic market. This variable measures how fierce the competition is between companies offering similar products or services in the same area and can be influenced by several factors, such as the number of competitors, their size, market share, and marketing strategies adopted. A high intensity of local competition implies that companies must put in more effort to maintain or increase their market share, using tools such as price reductions, improvements in product or service quality, and innovation to differentiate themselves from the competition. In this context, competitive pressure can drive companies to continuously improve their operations and customer offerings. Conversely, a low intensity of local competition could indicate that there are few competing companies, or that the present businesses do not engage much in direct competition, allowing each to maintain a more stable position without significant efforts to attract customers. The intensity of local competition can significantly impact a company's profitability, influencing prices, profit margins, and innovation. A highly competitive market tends to be more dynamic but may also present greater challenges for business survival, particularly for new entrants or small companies. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2020.

Intensity of Local Competition in 2020. The intensity of local competition is a crucial parameter for evaluating the competitive pressure among companies in a given market. The provided data offers an overview of global differences in this aspect, showing how local competition varies from country to country. By analyzing the overall picture, we can see that more developed and highly industrialized markets tend to have higher competition intensity, while emerging or developing markets show relatively lower local competition. At the top of the ranking, we find Japan with a score of 87.2, followed by Hong Kong (85.6), the United States (84.3), and South Korea (83.9). These countries are known for their highly competitive and dynamic economies, characterized by a large number of active companies in key markets such as technology, industrial manufacturing, and financial services. For example, Japan and South Korea are global leaders in electronics and technological innovation, where competition is particularly intense. The presence of large conglomerates, coupled with a strong culture of innovation, contributes to increasing competitive pressure. Hong Kong stands out as one of the world's major financial centers, where the intensity of local competition is driven by a high number of banks, investment companies, and other financial institutions. In this environment, companies must compete not only at the local level but also with international players operating in a highly integrated market. Hong Kong's position is further strengthened by its proximity to mainland China, which makes competition even fiercer, particularly in sectors related to trade and logistics. The United States ranks third, reaffirming its role as a global leader in technology, innovation, and services. Silicon Valley, for example, is a symbol of fierce competition, where technology companies of all sizes compete for leadership in sectors such as artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and automation. This high competition has enabled the United States to maintain a dominant position in

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global markets and to continuously stimulate innovation. Looking at Europe, countries like the Netherlands (80.5), France (80.0), and the United Kingdom (79.9) also show high local competition intensity. In these markets, the high competition is partly due to the density of businesses and strong economic integration within the European Union. The Netherlands, for example, is an important logistics and trade hub, facilitated by the presence of one of Europe's largest ports, Rotterdam, which generates fierce competition among companies in the transportation and logistics sector. Similarly, France and the United Kingdom, with diversified and advanced economies, experience intense competition in sectors such as fashion, finance, and technology services. In the Middle East, Turkey (80.5) and Israel (75.4) are among the countries with the highest levels of competition. Turkey is an emerging economy, and local competition is fueled by its strategic position between Europe and Asia, making it a transit point for many trade routes. Israel, on the other hand, is known for its advanced technology sector, often referred to as the "Startup Nation," where competition among young tech companies is particularly intense, especially in the fields of cybersecurity and military technologies. Moving down the ranking, we see a decline in the intensity of local competition in emerging and developing countries. Brazil (68.2), India (67.6), Bangladesh (67.5), and Nigeria (68.7) have significantly lower scores compared to advanced economies. This can be attributed to several factors, including a lower density of businesses, less diversified economies, and underdeveloped infrastructures, which reduce opportunities for direct competition. However, even though local competition is less intense, these markets offer great growth opportunities for international companies, given the increasing domestic demand and growing openness to global markets. For example, in India, local competition is growing, particularly in sectors such as technology and e-commerce, where companies like Amazon and Flipkart compete to dominate the market. However, many traditional sectors remain less competitive due to regulatory and infrastructural barriers. At the bottom of the ranking, we find countries like Iran (58.0), Croatia (57.1), Argentina (55.4), and Ethiopia (45.6). These countries show relatively low local competition, often due to economic or political factors that limit the development of competitive markets. In Iran, for example, international economic sanctions and government control over many sectors of the economy have reduced the possibility of open competition among private companies. Similarly, in Ethiopia, the low intensity of competition is partly due to a lack of adequate infrastructure and an economy still heavily based on agriculture. In Argentina, economic instability, high inflation, and frequent financial crises have made it difficult for businesses to compete effectively, leading to a less dynamic market compared to other economies in the region. Although Argentina has significant potential in sectors such as agriculture and natural resources, economic uncertainty continues to hinder the development of more intense local competition. The data clearly shows that the intensity of local competition varies significantly between countries, reflecting economic, cultural, and political differences. In advanced markets like Japan, the United States, and South Korea, competition is driven by innovation, business density, and sophisticated consumers. In emerging countries, competition is growing but is often hindered by factors such as lack of infrastructure and limited access to international markets. Finally, in countries with low competition intensity, economic and political barriers continue to limit the growth of the private sector and the expansion of market opportunities.

Intensity of Local Competition between 2013 and 2020. The analysis of data on the intensity of local competition in various countries between 2013 and 2021 reveals significant trends in global markets, with some economies experiencing an increase in internal competition while others have seen a decline. The intensity of local competition is an important measure of economic dynamism, as a high level of competition between companies can foster innovation, improve the quality of products and

services, and reduce prices for consumers. One notable trend emerging from the data is the significant increase in the intensity of local competition in several countries, particularly those that are emerging or developing. A striking example is Guinea, which recorded an impressive increase of 24.6 points between 2013 and 2021, with a percentage change of 47.95%. This may reflect an acceleration of industrialization and greater participation of local businesses in the global market, thus intensifying competition. Another country that has experienced a significant increase in local competition is Armenia, with an absolute change of 26.1 points and a percentage change of 54.95%. In this case, we can hypothesize that improvements in the economic environment and the liberalization of markets have facilitated the growth of the number of active businesses, stimulating internal competition. The same applies to countries like Serbia (+20.5 points) and Albania (+19.8 points), both experiencing strong economic growth in the post-global financial crisis period. Additionally, the increase in local competition intensity in countries like Colombia (+13.1 points), Honduras (+10.3 points), and Vietnam (+10.5 points) suggests that these markets are evolving towards more open and dynamic economic models. The integration of these countries into global value chains may have contributed to stimulating greater local competition, particularly in the manufacturing and services sectors. Even some developed economies have seen an increase in competition intensity. The United States, for example, saw an increase of 6.9 points with a percentage change of 8.91%. This increase can be attributed to technological innovation and the emergence of new industries, such as technology and e-commerce, which have introduced dynamic and continuous competition. Silicon Valley, as a global technology hub, has fostered fierce competition among startups and industry giants, contributing to the overall result. Japan has also seen an increase in local competition intensity, with a rise of 3.1 points and a percentage change of 3.69%. The country is known for its highly competitive economic environment, especially in the automotive and electronics sectors. Continuous innovation and pressure on profit margins in these sectors may have further driven competition intensity. It is also interesting to observe the increase seen in countries like France (+5.4 points) and the United Kingdom, although the latter registered a slight decline in 2021 compared to the previous peak. These data reflect a European market that, despite the difficulties related to Brexit and the pandemic, continues to maintain a high level of competition, particularly in sectors such as fashion, finance, and advanced technologies. On the other hand, some countries have experienced a decrease in local competition intensity. The Netherlands, Germany, and Belgium have seen declines of 4.1 points, 3.5 points, and 4.1 points, respectively, with negative percentage changes ranging between 4.85% and 4.96%. These results may indicate market saturation or business consolidation, where a few dominant players reduce direct competition among companies. In mature markets, mergers and acquisitions and business concentration can be factors contributing to lower competition. Specifically, the decline in competition intensity in the Netherlands and Germany may be linked to increasing regulation and the predominant role of large companies, which can discourage competition from small and medium-sized enterprises. Moreover, these countries have highly advanced economies, and some stabilization in competition levels may be natural in mature markets. Even in some emerging or developing countries, a reduction in local competition intensity is observed. In India, for example, competition intensity decreased by 5.3 points with a percentage change of 7.27%. This data may be surprising, considering that India is one of the largest and most dynamic emerging economies in the world. However, factors such as regulatory barriers, bureaucratic complexity, and difficulty in doing business may have contributed to limiting the growth of internal competition, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises. Similarly, countries like Qatar (-13.3 points) and Sri Lanka (-9.6 points) have experienced significant declines, which could be attributed to economic crises, political instability, or greater state control over certain key sectors. In Qatar, for example, the economy's heavy dependence on the energy sector may have limited the development of other sectors, thus reducing local competition. Another important observation concerns significant regional differences.

African countries like Nigeria (+9.8 points) and Kenya (+6.5 points) have seen an increase in local competition, suggesting that some African economies are rapidly evolving, with a growing number of businesses vying for the domestic market. These emerging markets are attracting increasing international investments, which could contribute to intensifying competition. In the context of Latin America, countries like Mexico (+7.4 points) and Ecuador (+14.9 points) also show an increase in competition intensity. This may be related to economic reforms and trade liberalization, which have fostered a more competitive environment. The analysis of data on local competition intensity from 2013 to 2021 highlights a global trend toward greater competition, particularly in emerging markets. However, there are also signs of consolidation and declining competition in some mature economies, likely due to market concentration and the emergence of dominant players. The dynamics of local competition are influenced by economic, political, and regulatory factors and vary significantly from country to country. Ultimately, the intensity of local competition remains a key indicator for understanding economic dynamism and growth prospects in different regions of the world.

Economic Policies to Promote the Intensity of Local Competition. Economic policies aimed at promoting local competition intensity are essential for improving market efficiency, stimulating innovation, reducing prices, and enhancing the quality of products and services offered to consumers. A competitive economy not only fosters technological progress and production efficiency but also encourages the creation of new businesses, increases social mobility, and contributes to overall economic growth. However, promoting competition requires particular attention from governments and regulatory bodies, which must implement targeted policies to remove obstacles to competition and create an environment conducive to the entry and growth of businesses. One of the main economic policy tools to increase local competition intensity is competition regulation. Through the introduction of antitrust laws and monitoring of unfair market practices, governments can prevent anti-competitive behavior, such as cartel formation, abuse of dominant positions, and mergers that reduce competition. Competition authorities play a key role in this process, monitoring markets and intervening when necessary to ensure that companies do not abuse their economic power. For example, heavy fines and sanctions can be imposed on companies attempting to monopolize the market or adopt anti-competitive practices such as predatory pricing or exclusive agreements. Another fundamental lever is the liberalization of closed or heavily regulated markets. In many countries, sectors such as energy, transportation, telecommunications, and financial services have traditionally been dominated by state monopolies or oligopolies, limiting competition and hindering the entry of new operators. Liberalizing these markets allows the entry of new players and stimulates competition, leading to greater efficiency and benefits for consumers. For example, the introduction of competition in the telecommunications sector in many countries has led to a significant reduction in prices and improved service quality. A critical factor in promoting local competition is also facilitating market entry for new businesses. High regulatory and bureaucratic barriers can prevent the entry of new players, limiting competition. Reforms that reduce startup costs, simplify licensing procedures, and decrease administrative burdens can have a significant impact on intensifying local competition. Such policies encourage entrepreneurship and allow small and medium-sized enterprises to enter and compete with larger, established players. Another crucial aspect is supporting innovation and research and development (R&D). Innovation is one of the main drivers of competition, as it introduces new products and services into the market, increases production efficiency, and reduces costs. Governments can incentivize innovation through direct grants, R&D tax credits, and the creation of public research institutions that collaborate with the private sector. Additionally, promoting open competition based on innovation requires effective protection of intellectual property

rights, ensuring that innovative companies are protected from plagiarism without creating unjustified barriers to the spread of new technologies. Efficient infrastructure is another key element in fostering local competition. In many countries, especially developing ones, the lack of adequate infrastructure represents a significant barrier to intensifying competition. Roads, ports, electrical grids, and digital infrastructure are essential for businesses to operate efficiently and compete with other market players. Governments can promote competition by investing in public infrastructure and encouraging the private sector to participate in infrastructure development through public-private partnerships. Another important area of intervention is trade policy. Opening up to international trade stimulates local competition, as domestic companies are forced to compete with foreign ones. Reducing tariff and non-tariff barriers, along with facilitating international exchanges, allows the entry of foreign goods and services, increasing competitive pressure on local producers and incentivizing them to improve their efficiency and innovation. However, trade policies must be carefully balanced, as excessive openness without adequate support measures can pose challenges for local businesses, especially in sectors that are still developing. Transparency and accessibility of information represent another fundamental aspect for increasing local competition. Markets function better when information on prices, products, and suppliers is easily accessible to all participants. Governments can implement measures to ensure that market information is public and easily accessible, reducing the possibility of large players exploiting their advantageous position to influence prices or adopt unfair practices. Digital technologies can play a key role in this context, facilitating the creation of online platforms for price comparison or transparency in public procurement tenders. Economic policies must also consider the role of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which are often more vulnerable to competition from large companies but play a crucial role in promoting a diversified and dynamic local economy. To support SMEs and enable them to compete effectively, governments can offer tax incentives, easier access to credit, and training programs. Additionally, promoting collaboration networks between SMEs and large companies can foster the growth of the former, allowing them to access new resources and expertise. The last important aspect is education and workforce training. A dynamic labor market, with highly skilled workers, increases local competitiveness, as companies can rely on a workforce prepared to meet the challenges of the global market. Policies that invest in education and continuous training are crucial to ensuring that workers can adapt to new technologies and the evolving needs of the market. Moreover, encouraging labor mobility within and between different sectors can help improve the efficiency of local markets. In summary, economic policies to promote local competition intensity must be multidimensional, embracing a combination of targeted regulations, market liberalization, support for innovation and SMEs, investments in infrastructure and human capital, and balanced trade openness. A holistic approach that takes into account the specific economic and political context of each country is essential to create an environment conducive to competition and sustainable economic growth.

Conclusions. The value of local competition intensity has grown on average in the countries considered by 64.10 units to a value of 68.54 units, representing an increase of +4.44 units, or 6.94%. There are countries where the value of local competition intensity has increased much more than the average value recorded for the countries considered between 2013 and 2020, including: Armenia with +54.95%, Algeria with +53.63%, Guinea with +47.95%, Serbia with +47.02%, and Russia with +43.52%. Conversely, there are countries where the value of local competition intensity has significantly decreased between 2013 and 2020, including: the United Arab Emirates with -9.21%, Sri Lanka with -12.82%, Hungary with -16.71%, Qatar with -16.86%, and Yemen with -18.31%. Considering middle-high income countries, the average local competition intensity value is 74.87.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/>

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